

Supplementary File 8: Additional Questionnaires Analyses

Self-Reported Physical Activity Level

The participants displayed heterogeneous levels of physical activity (see Figure S1). They engaged most in walking (i.e., a low-intensity activity; $M = 3,757.6$ metabolic equivalent [MET], $SD = 3,057.5$), followed by vigorous-intensity activities ($M = 3,185.6$ MET, $SD = 4,255.3$), and moderate-intensity activities ($M = 2,407.1$, $SD = 3,886.4$).

Motivation to Engage in Physical Activity

The Behavioural Regulations in Exercise Questionnaire (BREQ-3; Markland & Tobin, 2004) was used to assess participants' motives for exercise. The exercise motives that were most endorsed by the participants were Identified ($M = 2.94$, $SD = 0.77$), Integrated ($M = 2.78$, $SD = 1.03$), and Intrinsic forms of regulation ($M = 3.35$, $SD = 0.63$). There was a high degree of heterogeneity evident with respect to Introjected Regulation ($M = 1.92$, $SD = 0.93$). The exercise motives least endorsed by the participants were External Regulation ($M = 0.33$, $SD = 1.25$) and Amotivation ($M = 0.05$, $SD = 0.13$). Overall, it was evident that the sample of participants was characterized by exercise motives representing a relatively high degree of self-determination.

Figure S1

Self-Reported Physical Activity Level

Note. Box plots and probability density functions are displayed for each intensity of physical activity. Each dot represents an individual participant. MET = metabolic equivalent.

Figure S2

Motivation to Engage in Physical Activity

Note. Each dot represents an individual participant. BREQ-3 = Behavioural Regulations in Exercise Questionnaire.

Tolerance of Exercise Intensity

The participants exhibited heterogeneous levels of tolerance of exercise intensity ($M = 3.17$; $SD = 0.88$) and preference for exercise intensity ($M = 3.17$; $SD = 0.80$; see Figure S3).

Figure S3

Tolerance of and Preference for Exercise Intensity

Note. Box plots are displayed for each scale. Each dot represents an individual participant. PRETIE-Q = Preference for and Tolerance of the Intensity of Exercise Questionnaire.

References

Markland, D., & Tobin, V. (2004). A modification to the Behavioural Regulation in Exercise Questionnaire to include an assessment of amotivation. *Journal of Sport & Exercise Psychology, 26*(2), 191–196.